

Impact Assessment of Sustainability Initiatives: Evaluation Methods

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ABSTRACT

Sustainability initiatives planning and implementation is a complex process that demands better decision-making capabilities. Improving decision-making capabilities call for impact assessment of different initiative in a given reference scenario. Impact assessment supports decision-makers to structure better policies for the future either by evaluating the outcome of existing policies or by anticipating the possible outcome of the initiative. The aim of this course work is to categorize available impact assessment methods in the case of sustainable initiatives besides their merit analysis.